

Risk factors for the incursion of highly pathogenic avian influenza virus into poultry and other captive bird holdings in Denmark from 2020 to 2023: A case-control study

Helene Ane Jensen^{a,*}, Søren Saxmose Nielsen^a, Carsten Thure Kirkeby^a, Matthew Denwood^a, Lene Jung Kjær^a, Yuan Liang^a, Charlotte Kristiane Hjulsgaard^b, Anette Ella Boklund^a

^a Department of Veterinary and Animal Sciences, University of Copenhagen, Grønnegårdsvej 8, Frederiksberg C 1870, Denmark

^b Department of Virus and Microbiological Special Diagnostics, Statens Serum Institut, Artillerivej 5, Copenhagen S 2300, Denmark

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Highly pathogenic avian influenza virus
Biosecurity
Monte Carlo integration
Outbreak

ABSTRACT

Highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI) is a major concern in terms of animal and human health. Between October 2020 and September 2023, there were 36 HPAI outbreaks detected in poultry and other captive birds in Denmark. However, it is often not possible to determine the exact route of introduction. We conducted a case-control study to compare the odds of exposure to a range of potential risk factors for HPAI virus incursion into Danish poultry or other captive bird holdings with HPAI outbreaks (cases) and with no HPAI outbreaks (controls) during the HPAI epidemiological seasons 2020/2021, 2021/2022 and 2022/2023. The owners of 38 % of the eligible case holdings and 45 % of the eligible control holdings declined to participate, suggesting that HPAI virus infection is a sensitive subject for some owners. The study population included 18 cases and 34 controls. We collected data primarily through questionnaire-based interviews and estimated odds ratios (OR) within a Bayesian framework using a Beta conjugate prior to define the odds directly, with Monte Carlo integration from these posterior distributions of odds to estimate the relevant OR with 95 % credible intervals (CI) and Bayesian p-values. The results indicated that the odds of observing wild waterfowl or gulls on the roof or around farm buildings compared to observing none within 500 m of the holding was higher for case holdings (OR: 18.7, 95 % CI: 3.1–148, p: 0.022). This information can be used for future risk-based monitoring, biosecurity management and placement of captive bird holdings.

1. Introduction

Highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI) is an infectious and notifiable disease in both poultry and other captive birds (terms are defined in the EU Animal Health Law (Regulation (EU) 2016/429, [European Union, 2016](#)) and by the [World Organisation for Animal Health 2021](#)). The disease generally has a high morbidity and mortality in most avian species. HPAI is caused by HPAI viruses, which have a high propensity to mutate and can cause zoonotic infections, making the viruses relevant to both animal and human health. Following an outbreak of HPAI in poultry, an affected country will lose its HPAI-free status within the European Union (EU) and the World Organisation for Animal Health (WOAH). The loss of free status can affect the trade of poultry and poultry products and can therefore have major economic consequences.

Within the EU, veterinary authorities manage outbreaks of HPAI by stamping out all domestic birds in affected holdings in accordance with the EU Animal Health Law (Regulation (EU) 2016/429, [European Union, 2016](#)). In Denmark, the owner of a holding where there is an outbreak is offered reimbursement of financial losses. However, farmers can still be affected, depending on e.g. the financial status of the holding, the compensation scheme and the amount of production downtime. Concerns about economic or social consequences can therefore affect the farmers' willingness to discuss the disease status of the holding ([Otte and Nugent, 2004](#)), which might result in bias in epidemiological investigations of HPAI.

During the epidemiological seasons 2020/2021, 2021/2022 and 2022/2023, Europe experienced 5479 outbreaks of HPAI in domestic birds ([European Food Safety Authority et al., 2022, 2023, 2024](#)).

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: helene.jensen@sund.ku.dk (H.A. Jensen).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prevetmed.2025.106419>

Received 25 September 2024; Received in revised form 20 December 2024; Accepted 2 January 2025

Available online 4 January 2025

0167-5877/© 2025 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

According to the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), an HPAI epidemiological season refers to the period from the beginning of October to the end of the following September (EFSA et al., 2024). Between October 2020 and September 2023, 36 HPAI outbreaks within domestic bird holdings resulted in the loss of more than 596,000 poultry and other captive birds in Denmark (Danish Veterinary and Food Administration, 2023a). In the same period, more than 700 dead wild birds, primarily species of the orders Anseriformes, Falconiformes and Charadriiformes, tested positive for HPAI virus in Denmark in the passive surveillance programme (Danish Veterinary and Food Administration, 2023b). After an outbreak of HPAI on a poultry or captive bird premise, the Danish veterinary authorities carry out follow-up epidemiological investigations aiming to determine potential introduction routes of the virus and potential transmission to other farms. The majority of HPAI outbreaks in domestic birds in Denmark have been characterised as primary outbreaks, where poultry and other captive birds were most likely to be infected through direct or indirect contact with wild birds, as opposed to local farm-to-farm transmission (known as secondary outbreaks). However, it is often not possible to determine the exact route of introduction.

Previous studies indicate that the following factors related to the holding and its environment affect the risk of HPAI infection: bird species or production system (Busani et al., 2009; Liu et al., 2024; Thomas et al., 2005), size of the holding (Busani et al., 2009), age of the birds (Elbers et al., 2007; Jerry et al., 2021), distance to the nearest outbreak holding or being in an existing restriction zone (Busani et al., 2009; Green et al., 2023; Patyk et al., 2023), densities of wild birds (Schreuder et al., 2022; Velkers et al., 2021), landscape type – more specifically distance to wetlands and coastal areas (Kjær et al., 2022; Liu et al., 2024; Shimizu et al., 2018; Walsh et al., 2020; Ward et al., 2008), and biosecurity measures (Garber et al., 2016; Green et al., 2023; Guinat et al., 2020; Patyk et al., 2023). The term “biosecurity” is defined in the EU Animal Health Law (Regulation (EU) 2016/429, 2021) and includes the following physical protection measures and management measures to reduce the risk of pathogen incursion: enclosing and netting, cleaning and disinfection, procedures for birds, vehicles, equipment and people entering and exiting the holding, and control of rodents that may serve as potential vectors of disease. As many outbreaks have been observed in holdings with high biosecurity standards across Europe (EFSA et al., 2022, 2023) and Denmark, there remains a knowledge gap about risk factors for HPAI incursion into poultry and other captive bird holdings.

The purpose of the study was to improve HPAI disease control by providing evidence of risk factors for HPAI virus incursion. Information obtained in this study will contribute to advancing the field of HPAI biosecurity research and can be used by risk managers in decisions about implementing mitigating actions. We aimed to assess potential risk factors for the incursion of HPAI virus into poultry or other captive bird holdings in Denmark. More specifically, the objective was to compare the odds of exposure to a range of potential risk factors for HPAI virus incursion into holdings with and without previous HPAI outbreaks during the epidemiological seasons 2020/2021, 2021/2022 and 2022/2023 in a case-control study. The potential risk factors of interest covered characteristics of the holding, buildings and surroundings, feeding and bedding practices, staff and visitors, biosecurity measures, heating and ventilation systems, observations of wild birds and rodents, and the trade of poultry and poultry products.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Setting

We carried out the study in Denmark, a country with a population of more than 29 million poultry and other captive birds distributed across 1000 establishments registered in the Central Husbandry Register (CHR) (CHR, 2023).

2.2. Study design

Due to the limited number of outbreaks, we chose a matched case-control study design (see matching variables below), which is described in detail in our study protocol (Jensen et al., 2023). We used the reporting guidelines described in the Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology – Veterinary (STROBE-Vet) Statement (Sargeant et al., 2016).

2.3. Target and study populations

The target population was poultry and other captive bird holdings in Denmark and potentially similar holdings in other countries. The study population included all recorded poultry and captive bird holdings in Denmark with and without HPAI outbreaks during the epidemiological seasons 2020/2021, 2021/2022 and 2022/2023 with owners or managers who agreed to participate in the study. The study unit was the individual poultry or captive bird holding.

Holdings were eligible as cases if they had a primary outbreak of HPAI during the epidemiological seasons 2020/2021, 2021/2022 or 2022/2023. We therefore excluded 1) holdings that were classified as likely secondary HPAI outbreaks (outbreaks that were epidemiologically linked to a previous outbreak during the same season) through virological analyses and epidemiological investigations and 2) any subsequent outbreaks in the same holding within the study period (i.e. for the holdings with more than one primary outbreak during the considered epidemiological seasons, only the most recent outbreak was included as a case to ensure that the case study subjects were independent).

For each included case, we randomly selected two matched controls. Matching was based on the size of the holding (<100, 101–10,000 or >10,000 birds), types of birds in the holding (turkeys, ducks and geese, pheasants, broilers, layers, or a mix of the bird orders Anseriformes and Galliformes) and the shortest distance from the holding to coastal areas or wetlands (0–1500 m, 1501–3000 m, 3001–4500 m, 4501–6000 m or 6001–7500 m, Table 1). Matched poultry and captive bird holdings were deemed to be eligible controls if they 1) were registered in the CHR, 2) had no previous HPAI outbreaks during the considered epidemiological seasons according to the Danish Veterinary and Food Administration and 3) were located on the mainland or islands accessible via a bridge. We excluded holdings located on islands without a bridge connection to the mainland due to time and budget constraints.

2.4. Power calculation

An *a priori* power calculation indicated that we would be able to obtain a minimum detectable odds ratio (OR) of 4.5 with a confidence level of 95 % and a power of 80 % if 24 cases plus two controls per case were included. For the calculation, we assumed that the prevalence of exposure to potential risk factors in control holdings was 20 %.

2.5. Data collection

Two scientific assistants and the first author contacted the source population by telephone. We first contacted the eligible case holdings and then contacted eligible matched control holdings in groups of ten from a randomly generated list of eligible controls.

We collected data primarily through questionnaire-based interviews with the owners or managers during a visit to their holding. Questions relating to the age of the poultry, characteristics of the staff, biosecurity measures and trade of poultry and poultry products were only directed at owners and managers of commercial holdings. In this study, we defined commercial holdings as those with more than 100 poultry, while non-commercial hobby holdings were defined as having less than 100 poultry or less than 100 other captive birds. This definition was based on the breakpoint of 100 captive birds often being used in Danish national legislation on biosecurity measures against avian influenza. The

questionnaire was available on paper, on a tablet and online in SurveyXact (Rambøll Management Consulting, Aarhus, Denmark; [Supplementary material 1](#)). Consent was obtained using a specific consent form and was required from each respondent ([Supplementary material 2](#)). In cases where data collectors filled out the questionnaire on paper, the data were subsequently entered into SurveyXact. For case holdings, interviews were conducted by one of three prioritised methods: 1) face-to-face interviews at the holdings, 2) telephone interviews or 3) e-mail questionnaires. These three options were required as some owners would not agree to interviews being held on their premises, and some owners had moved away from the holding or no longer kept poultry or other captive birds. For the control holdings, only methods 1 and 2 were used. We collected data from March to December 2023. After collection, the data were anonymised.

2.6. Outcome variable

The outcome variable of the study was an HPAI outbreak, i.e. the dichotomous classification of cases and controls. The Danish Veterinary and Food Administration provided information about holdings with previous outbreaks. The Danish National Reference Laboratory for Avian Influenza at Statens Serum Institut (SSI) had detected HPAI in the outbreak holdings using polymerase chain reaction (PCR) followed by sequencing. All holdings registered in the CHR and not reported as cases were considered potential controls, based on the lack of clinical signs.

2.7. Explanatory variables

The study's 48 explanatory variables were dichotomous, nominal or ordinal. They included a range of potential risk factors covering characteristics of the holding, buildings and surroundings (four variables, [Table 2](#)), feeding and bedding practices (seven variables, [Table 3](#)), staff and visitors (six variables, [Table 4](#)), biosecurity measures (12 variables, [Table 5](#)), heating and ventilation systems (five variables, [Table 6](#)), observations of wild birds and rodents (five variables, [Table 7](#)) and the trade and collection of poultry and poultry products (nine variables, [Table 8](#)). The variables of interest were included in the questionnaire and each variable, the variable type and hypotheses linked to each variable are listed in our study protocol ([Jensen et al., 2023](#)). Due to the small dataset, assessment of confounding constitutes a challenge. To evaluate potential confounding, we planned to use Pearson's Chi-square test to assess if statistically significant risk factors were associated with non-significant explanatory variables with at least five observations in each group. We then planned to offer the associated variables to the model and consider confounding to be likely if the parameter estimates of statistically significant variables changed by more than 20 %, when including another variable to the model. However, since none of the explanatory variables that were not statistically significant had at least five observations in each group ([Table S1 in Supplementary material 3](#)), Pearson's Chi-square test was not performed.

2.8. Bias

We identified and assessed potential biases in the study using a tool for rapid assessment of risk of bias named raRoB ([Plate et al., 2024](#)). We reduced some confounding bias by matching the cases and controls. To minimise information bias, we formulated all questions in the questionnaire *a priori*, and a number of test interviews were conducted before data collection began. We reduced response bias by assuring the respondents that all data would be anonymised.

2.9. Descriptive statistics

We described the variables of interest stratified by cases and controls and summarised the variables using proportions and frequencies. We also listed the reasons for lack of participation in case and control

groups.

2.10. Analytical statistics

We used hypothesis testing based on the hypotheses listed in our study protocol ([Jensen et al., 2023](#)). Due to the presence of (quasi-) separated data (partly resulting from the relatively small sample size), we were unable to estimate the OR for all risk factors using standard logistic regression. We therefore analysed our data within a Bayesian framework, using a minimally informative Beta(1,1) conjugate prior to define the posterior distribution of odds for each risk factor directly. We then used Monte Carlo integration to derive the relevant OR and calculated mean estimates for the OR along with 95 % credible intervals (CI) and Bayesian p-values. All analyses were done in R (version 4.3.3, [R Core Team, 2024](#)) using the packages “coda” ([Plummer et al., 2006](#)), “dplyr” ([Wickham et al., 2023](#)) and “writexl” ([Ooms, 2024](#)). A lower confidence limit of 1 or above and a Bayesian p-value of 0.05 were used as the cutoff for statistically significant differences. We corrected the p-values for multiple comparisons using the Holm method ([Holm, 1979](#)).

3. Results

3.1. Population

During the considered epidemiological seasons, the Danish Veterinary and Food Administration declared 36 outbreaks of HPAI in poultry or other captive birds. Four of the 36 outbreaks were not eligible for inclusion in the study as they were classified as likely secondary outbreaks, while a further three outbreaks were not eligible due to repeated outbreaks within the same holding. The remaining 29 outbreaks were eligible for inclusion as cases and were invited to participate in the study. Owners of 11 of the 29 eligible cases declined to participate for the following reasons: time constraints ($n = 1$), the questionnaire was sent to the owner, but it was never returned ($n = 2$), concerns that the study results would lead to more legislative restrictions ($n = 1$), they did not want to participate because they believed they already knew the reason for HPAI incursion into the holding ($n = 2$), they had compliance issues with the Danish Veterinary and Food Administration ($n = 1$), they did not want to participate without further explanation ($n = 2$), data collectors were not able to contact the owner ($n = 2$). This resulted in 18 case holdings included in the study: four commercial broiler holdings, four commercial turkey holdings, four non-commercial holdings with hens, three non-commercial holdings with both Anseriformes and Galliformes, two commercial holdings with laying hens, and one commercial holding with pheasants ([Table 1](#)). Five of the included cases had an outbreak of HPAI during the 2020/2021 season, six had an outbreak during the 2021/2022 season and seven included cases had an outbreak during the 2022/2023 season.

We invited 62 owners of eligible controls to participate in the study, 28 of whom declined to participate due to the following reasons: time constraints ($n = 22$), they did not want visitors at their holding due to biosecurity ($n = 2$), personal issues ($n = 1$), they believed the questionnaire was too long ($n = 1$), they had already participated in another project ($n = 1$), they did not want to participate as they assumed vaccines would prevent HPAI outbreaks in the future ($n = 1$). A total of 34 controls were thus included in the study: two matched controls for each of 16 cases, and one matched control for each of two case holdings with turkeys. We were unable to identify and include more turkey holding controls as all owners of turkey holdings in Denmark had already been contacted. In addition, for one of the turkey holdings with two matched controls, one of the controls did not match the category of shortest distance to coast and wetlands.

Owners of seven case holdings and 24 control holdings were interviewed during a visit to their holdings, while owners of ten case holdings and ten control holdings were interviewed by telephone and one owner

Table 1

Characteristics of the study population in a case-control study to estimate risk factors for the incursion of highly pathogenic avian influenza virus into poultry and other captive bird holdings in Denmark from 2020 to 2023.

Variables and levels		Case (n = 18)	Control (n = 34)
Commercial holdings or non-commercial hobby holdings	Herd size*		
	Non-commercial hobby holdings	< 100	7 (39 %)
Commercial holdings	101–10,000	2 (11 %)	4 (12 %)
	> 10,000	9 (50 %)	16 (47 %)
Non-commercial hobby holdings	Type of birds*		
	Chickens	4 (22 %)	8 (24 %)
Commercial holdings	Anseriformes and Galliformes	3 (17 %)	6 (18 %)
	Layers	2 (11 %)	4 (12 %)
	Broilers	4 (22 %)	8 (24 %)
	Turkeys	4 (22 %)	6 (18 %)
Shortest distance to wetlands or coast (m)*	Pheasants	1 (6 %)	2 (6 %)
	0–1500	9 (50 %)	18 (53 %)
	1501–3000	5 (28 %)	8 (24 %)
	3001–4500	1 (6 %)	3 (9 %)
	4501–6000	2 (11 %)	3 (9 %)
	6001–7500	1 (6 %)	2 (6 %)
Data collection	Visit	7 (39 %)	24 (71 %)
	Telephone	10 (56 %)	10 (29 %)
	E-mail	1 (6 %)	0 (0 %)
Region	Central Denmark Region	3 (17 %)	6 (18 %)
	Region Zealand	9 (50 %)	12 (35 %)
	The Capital Region of Denmark	3 (17 %)	4 (12 %)
	The North Denmark Region	0 (0 %)	4 (12 %)
	The Region of Southern Denmark	3 (17 %)	8 (24 %)

* Variables describing the size of the holding (number of birds), type of birds and shortest distance to wetlands or coast in metres were matched between case and control holdings.

of a case holding filled out the questionnaire via e-mail (Table 1).

3.2. Descriptive statistics

The descriptive statistics are presented in Tables 2–8. Some groups had too few observations for analytical statistics. Therefore, before the analytical statistics, the variables were reconsidered and the levels were regrouped to enhance the interpretation while maintaining meaningful groupings. For example, levels describing different types of outdoor access (outdoor area either with fixed roof, outdoor area with and without fixed roof or outdoor area without fixed roof) were included in one group containing all holdings where birds had any outdoor access (Table 2). The original categorisation is available in the questionnaire in Supplementary material 1.

Characteristics of the holding, buildings and surroundings (Table 2). Around half of the case and control holdings had no access to outdoor areas (50 % and 47 %, respectively), and the other half had access to an outdoor area either with some form of coverage such as a fixed roof, net or vegetation (seven cases and 14 controls) or without any form of coverage (two cases and four controls). The median age of the birds in the commercial case holdings was higher than in the commercial control holdings at the time of the case outbreaks. Only one case and three controls were located in urban or suburban areas, while the rest of the study population was surrounded by open land without trees (ten cases and nine controls) or with trees or in a forest area (seven cases and 22 controls).

Feeding and bedding (Table 3). Most cases and controls were fed indoors (83 % and 85 %, respectively). Feed spillage was observed in one

Table 2

Descriptive statistics of variables related to characteristics of the holding, buildings and surroundings stratified by cases and controls in a case-control study to estimate risk factors for the incursion of highly pathogenic avian influenza virus into poultry and other captive bird holdings in Denmark from 2020 to 2023. The question regarding the age of the poultry was only directed to commercial holdings (11 cases and 20 controls).

Variables and levels ^a	Case (n = 11)	Control (n = 20)	
Age of the poultry^b	Up to 18 weeks old	2 (18 %)	3 (15 %)
	More than 18 weeks old	5 (45 %)	3 (15 %)
	Do not recall	4 (36 %)	14 (70 %)
		Case (n = 18)	Control (n = 34)
Number of houses	1 or 2	7 (39 %)	20 (59 %)
	3 or more	11 (61 %)	14 (41 %)
	Indoor vs. outdoor access	Outdoor ^c	9 (50 %)
Indoor		9 (50 %)	16 (47 %)
Surroundings	Urban or suburban area	1 (6 %)	3 (9 %)
	Open land	10 (56 %)	9 (26 %)
	Open land with trees or forest area	7 (39 %)	22 (65 %)

^a We asked the owners or managers of the case holdings about the specific period during which the outbreak was detected, and the controls about the period during which the outbreak was detected in the matched case.

^b The age of the poultry in weeks. Only the owners of holdings with more than 100 poultry were asked this question (11 cases and 20 controls).

^c Access to outdoor area with a fixed roof, outdoor area with and without a fixed roof or outdoor area without a fixed roof.

of two case farms and 4 of 21 control farms. It was not possible to check for feed spillage for the 11 cases and ten controls where owners or managers were interviewed by telephone or e-mail.

Staff and visitors (Table 4). Some owners did not recall information about challenges relating to communication among staff (three controls) or changes in staff (three cases and nine controls) around the time of the outbreak (for controls, the time of outbreak in the matched case). None of the owners of commercial case holdings reported any communication challenges or changes in staff, while only one owner of a control holding had experienced communication challenges and a change in staff around the time of the outbreak in the matched case.

Biosecurity measures (Table 5). Most of the commercial cases and controls (82 % and 85 %, respectively) had a hygiene lock with a clean and unclean zone before entrance into the holding. We observed the hygiene locks in one case holding and five control holdings, all of which had indications of regular use. We could not observe whether the hygiene lock had any indications of regular use at holdings where owners were interviewed by telephone. There were no substantial differences in the percentage use of biosecurity measures between commercial case and control holdings.

Heating and ventilation (Table 6). To protect poultry or other captive birds from wild birds and wild bird droppings, 61 % percent of the case holdings and 53 % of the control holdings had protected either the air intake, the air outtake or both with e.g. bird dropping trays, hoods or netting.

Observations of wild birds and rodents (Table 7). All case holdings and most control holdings (100 % and 79 %, respectively) were surrounded by habitats that are attractive to wild birds, such as crops, lakes and trees. Around the time of case detection, more owners of case holdings had observed wild waterfowl or gulls on the roof or around buildings (61 %) compared to control holdings (15 %). Additionally, fewer case holdings tended to have bird deterrents on the property (6 %) compared to control holdings (24 %).

Table 3

Descriptive statistics of variables related to *feeding and bedding* stratified by cases and controls in a case-control study to estimate risk factors for the incursion of highly pathogenic avian influenza virus into poultry and other captive bird holdings in Denmark from 2020 to 2023.

Variables and levels ^a	Case (n = 18)	Control (n = 34)
Feeding location		
Indoor	15 (83 %)	29 (85 %)
Outdoor	3 (17 %)	5 (15 %)
Feeding with leftovers or kitchen waste	3 (17 %)	10 (29 %)
Storage of concentrate		
Barrel, sack or similar	7 (39 %)	16 (47 %)
Silo	11 (61 %)	18 (53 %)
Feed spillage around storage unit with concentrate ^b		
Yes	1 (50 %)	4 (19 %)
No	1 (50 %)	17 (81 %)
Do not know ^c	5 ^d	2 ^d
Data collected by telephone or e-mail (i.e. not observed)	11 ^d	10 ^d
Question skipped	0 ^d	1 ^d
Allocation of bedding, hay and other roughage		
Daily/weekly/monthly	9 (50 %)	18 (53 %)
When introducing new birds or less often	8 (44 %)	16 (47 %)
Do not recall	1 (6 %) ^e	0 (0 %)
Storage of straw, hay and other roughage		
Exposure to wild birds	6 (33 %)	9 (26 %)
No exposure to wild birds	9 (50 %)	21 (62 %)
Straw, hay and other roughage not used	3 (17 %)	4 (12 %)
Vehicles and equipment		
Exposure to wild birds	6 (33 %)	14 (41 %)
No exposure to wild birds	10 (56 %)	19 (56 %)
No vehicles or equipment used	2 (11 %)	1 (3 %)

^a We asked the owners or managers of the case holdings about the specific period during which the outbreak was detected, and the controls about the period during which the outbreak was detected in the matched case.

^b The question was answered by the interviewer after observing the storage unit with concentrate.

^c Two of the case holdings were not repopulated after the outbreak so feed storage was no longer present. For the remaining three case holdings and two control holdings in the “do not know” category, the interviewer did not observe the feed storage during the visit.

^d The categories “do not know”, “data collected by telephone or e-mail” and “question skipped” were not included in the calculation of proportions.

^e The case holding was not repopulated after the outbreak.

3.3. Analytical statistics

We identified observations of wild waterfowl or gulls on the roof or around buildings as the only statistically significant risk factor for the incursion of HPAI virus. More specifically, the odds of observing wild waterfowl or gulls on the roof or around farm buildings compared to observing none within 500 m of the holding were higher in case holdings (OR: 18.7, 95 % CI: 3.1–148, adjusted p: 0.022; Table 9). The remaining variables of interest listed in Tables 2–8 were not statistically significant based on 95 % CI and p-values at the 0.05 level. None of the cross-tabulations between the statistically significant variable and each of the remaining variables fulfilled the requirement to have at least five observations in all groups (Table S1 in Supplementary material 3), and therefore we did not perform Pearson’s Chi-square test.

4. Discussion

4.1. Summary and discussion of results

The objective of this case-control study was to assess potential risk factors for the incursion of HPAI virus into poultry and other captive bird holdings in Denmark. Out of 48 potential risk factors, the only statistically significant risk factor was observations of wild waterfowl or gulls on the roof or around buildings. There are several factors that may explain a high density of wild birds around poultry and captive bird

Table 4

Descriptive statistics of variables related to *staff and visitors* stratified by cases and controls in a case-control study to estimate risk factors for the incursion of highly pathogenic avian influenza virus into poultry and other captive bird holdings in Denmark from 2020 to 2023. The questions regarding staff were only directed to commercial holdings (11 cases and 20 controls).

Variables and levels ^a	Case (n = 11)	Control (n = 20)
Number of staff		
1 or 2	7 (64 %)	11 (55 %)
3 or more	4 (36 %)	9 (45 %)
Communication challenges		
Yes, often	0 (0 %)	1 (5 %)
No, or rarely	11 (100 %)	16 (80 %)
Do not recall	0 (0 %)	3 (16 %)
Number of languages spoken among staff		
1	6 (55 %)	12 (63 %)
2	5 (46 %)	7 (37 %)
Change in staff		
Yes	0 (0 %)	1 (5 %)
No	8 (73 %)	10 (50 %)
Do not recall	3 (27 %)	9 (45 %)
	Case (n = 18)	Control (n = 34)
Visits by veterinarian		
1–4 visits per month	6 (33 %)	7 (21 %)
1–4 visits per year	5 (28 %)	12 (35 %)
Never/only when needed	7 (39 %)	15 (44 %)
Other visitors		
1–4 visits per month	7 (39 %)	13 (38 %)
1–4 visits per year	0 (0 %)	2 (6 %)
Never/only when needed	11 (61 %)	19 (56 %)

^a We asked the owners or managers of the case holdings about the specific period during which the outbreak was detected, and the controls about the period during which the outbreak was detected in the matched case.

Table 5

Descriptive statistics of *biosecurity measures* stratified by cases and controls in a case-control study to estimate risk factors for the incursion of highly pathogenic avian influenza virus into poultry and other captive bird holdings in Denmark from 2020 to 2023. Only commercial holdings are included in this table (11 cases and 20 controls).

Variables and levels ^a	Case (n = 11)	Control (n = 20)
Education or instructions for staff about biosecurity within 5 years of case detection	9 (82 %)	17 (85 %)
Quarantine requirement	9 (82 %)	15 (75 %)
Presence of hygiene lock	9 (82 %)	17 (85 %)
Indication of regular use of hygiene lock ^b		
Yes	1 (100 %)	5 (100 %)
No	0 (0 %)	0 (0 %)
Data collected by telephone (i.e. not observed)	7 ^c	10 ^c
Skipped question	1 ^c	2 ^c
Showering before entrance	3 (27 %)	6 (30 %)
Change of clothes before entrance	9 (82 %)	16 (80 %)
Change of footwear before entrance	10 (91 %)	17 (85 %)
Hand wash before entrance	9 (82 %)	16 (80 %)
Hand disinfection before entrance	8 (73 %)	15 (75 %)
Footwear disinfection before entrance	1 (11 %)	3 (15 %)
Use of mask	5 (45 %)	6 (30 %)
Written instructions about biosecurity	8 (73 %)	16 (80 %)

^a We asked the owners or managers of the case holdings about the specific period during which the outbreak was detected, and the controls about the period during which the outbreak was detected in the matched case.

^b This question was only relevant if the holding had a hygiene lock (a total of 9 cases and 17 controls). The question was answered by the interviewer after observing the hygiene lock. An indication of irregular use might include for example spiderwebs in the sink.

^c The categories “data collected by telephone (i.e. not observed)” and “skipped question” were not included in the calculation of proportions.

Table 6

Descriptive statistics of variables related to *heating and ventilation* stratified by cases and controls in a case-control study to estimate risk factors for the incursion of highly pathogenic avian influenza virus into poultry and other captive bird holdings in Denmark from 2020 to 2023.

Variables and levels ^a	Case (n = 18)	Control (n = 34)
Heating of houses	7 (39 %)	15 (44 %)
Ventilation type ^b		
Negative pressure	8 (44 %)	15 (44 %)
Neutral pressure	5 (28 %)	4 (12 %)
Natural	13 (72 %)	22 (65 %)
Ventilation inlet ^b		
Roof	3 (17 %)	5 (15 %)
Wall	11 (61 %)	27 (79 %)
Ceiling	7 (39 %)	10 (29 %)
Ventilation outlet ^b		
Roof	6 (33 %)	13 (38 %)
Wall	8 (44 %)	20 (59 %)
Ceiling	5 (28 %)	10 (29 %)
Ventilation protected from wild birds/wild bird droppings ^{b,c}		
Inlet	11 (61 %)	18 (53 %)
Outlet	11 (61 %)	16 (47 %)

^a We asked the owners or managers of the case holdings about the specific period during which the outbreak was detected, and the controls about the period during which the outbreak was detected in the matched case.

^b More than one answer could be selected.

^c For example, bird dropping trays, hoods or netting.

Table 7

Descriptive statistics of variables related to *observations of wild birds and rodents* around the time of case detection stratified by cases and controls in a case-control study to estimate risk factors for the incursion of highly pathogenic avian influenza virus into poultry and other captive bird holdings in Denmark from 2020 to 2023.

Variables and levels ^a	Case (n = 18)	Control (n = 34)
Surroundings attractive to wild birds, e.g. crops, lakes and trees	18 (100 %)	27 (79 %)
Observations of wild waterfowl (Anseriformes) or gulls		
None within 500 m	1 (6 %)	13 (38 %)
Any number 500 m from holding	1 (6 %)	5 (15 %)
Any number 20 m from holding	5 (28 %)	11 (32 %)
Any number on roof or around buildings	11 (61 %)	5 (15 %)
Observations of wild birds other than waterfowl or gulls		
None within 500 m	1 (6 %)	3 (9 %)
Any number 500 m from holding	7 (39 %)	9 (26 %)
Any number on roof or around buildings	10 (56 %)	22 (65 %)
Use of wild bird deterrents, e.g. scarecrows, reflectors or gas cannons	1 (6 %)	8 (24 %)
Presence of rodents according to owner/manager		
1: None	5 (28 %)	2 (6 %)
2: Minimal	6 (33 %)	19 (56 %)
3: Moderate	6 (33 %)	9 (26 %)
4: High	1 (6 %)	2 (6 %)
5: Severe	0 (0 %)	2 (6 %)

^a We asked the owners or managers of the case holdings about the specific period during which the outbreak was detected, and the controls about the period during which the outbreak was detected in the matched case.

holdings. Firstly, we found that surroundings that are attractive to wild birds were common around the included holdings, where 100 % of the case holdings and 79 % of the control holdings were surrounded by crops, lakes or trees (Table 7), which may attract waterfowl and gulls in particular. Additionally, Denmark is in the path of major bird migration routes (Bregnballe et al., 1997; Dick et al., 1987; Tøttrup et al., 2018), which leads to numerous wild birds stopping over at certain times of the year. This increases the risk of HPAI virus transmission from other countries. Moreover, game birds are released into nature for hunting activities in Denmark every year (Kanstrup et al., 2009) and may seek

Table 8

Descriptive statistics of variables related to the *trade and collection of poultry and poultry products* stratified by cases and controls in a case-control study to estimate risk factors for the incursion of highly pathogenic avian influenza virus into poultry and other captive bird holdings in Denmark from 2020 to 2023. Only commercial holdings (11 cases and 20 controls) are included for the questions related to slaughter and trade.

Variables and levels ^a	Case (n = 11)	Control (n = 20)
Sending birds to slaughter		
Yes (different intervals per year)	9 (82 %)	12 (60 %)
No (never)	2 (18 %)	8 (40 %)
Capture method when sending birds to slaughter ^b		
Manually, own staff	2 (22 %)	2 (17 %)
Manually, external staff	3 (33 %)	6 (50 %)
Machine	4 (44 %)	4 (33 %)
Emptying entire house when sending to slaughter ^b	9 (100 %)	12 (100 %)
Sending birds to other holdings or releasing (game birds)		
Yes (different intervals per year)	2 (18 %)	8 (40 %)
No (never)	9 (82 %)	12 (60 %)
Emptying entire house when sending birds to other holdings or releasing ^c	1 (50 %)	7 (88 %)
Trade of eggs		
Daily or weekly	5 (45 %)	7 (35 %)
Never or rarely	6 (55 %)	13 (65 %)
	Case (n = 18)	Control (n = 34)
Purchase of new birds		
Weekly or monthly	1 (6 %)	5 (15 %)
1–4 times per year	13 (72 %)	19 (56 %)
Never or rarely	4 (22 %)	10 (29 %)
Collection of dead birds by rendering plant		
Weekly or monthly	8 (44 %)	14 (41 %)
1–4 times per year	4 (22 %)	3 (9 %)
Never or rarely	6 (33 %)	17 (50 %)
Delivery of feed and bedding		
Weekly or monthly	13 (72 %)	21 (62 %)
1–4 times per year	3 (17 %)	9 (26 %)
Rarely/when needed	2 (11 %)	2 (6 %)
Do not know	0 (0 %)	2 (6 %)

^a We asked the owners or managers of the case holdings about the specific period during which the outbreak was detected, and the controls about the period during which the outbreak was detected in the matched case.

^b This question was only relevant if the owner sent birds to slaughter (a total of 9 cases and 13 controls).

^c This question was only relevant if the owner sent birds to other holdings or released them if they were game birds (a total of 2 cases and 8 controls).

Table 9

Comparing the levels of *observations (of any number) of wild waterfowl or gulls* on roofs or around buildings, 20 m from the holding, 500 m from the holding and no observations within 500 m of the holding, reported as odds ratios (OR), 95 % credible intervals (CI) and Bayesian p-values in a case-control study to estimate risk factors for the incursion of highly pathogenic avian influenza virus into poultry and other captive bird holdings in Denmark from 2020 to 2023.

Observations of wild waterfowl or gulls	Mean OR (95 % CI)	Crude p-value	Adjusted p-value*
On roof or around buildings vs. 20 m from holding	4.4 (1.1–18.2)	0.019	1
On roof or around buildings vs. 500 m from holding	7.6 (1.1–61.9)	0.017	1
On roof or around buildings vs. none within 500 m of holding	18.7 (3.1–148)	< 0.001	0.022
20 m from holding vs. 500 m from holding	1.8 (0.3–13.5)	0.301	1
20 m from holding vs. none within 500 m of holding	4.3 (0.7–30.9)	0.057	1
500 m from holding vs. none within 500 m of holding	2.5 (0.2–29.2)	0.224	1

* p-values were corrected for multiple comparisons using the Holm method.

areas with crops, lakes or trees that are in close proximity to domestic bird holdings. Migrating birds may carry HPAI virus which can spill-over to environments with which poultry or captive birds are in direct or indirect contact. This risk of spill-over may explain our finding that the odds of observing waterfowl or gulls close to the holding were higher in case holdings, and it underlines the role of wild birds in the transmission of HPAI virus to domestic birds. However, to mitigate the risk we need to further investigate the route of introduction, i.e. what brings the virus from a highly contaminated environment into commercial farms with high levels of biosecurity, and are there any additional measures that can be provided.

4.2. Bias and study limitations

The main limitations of the study are the small sample size and non-response bias. Additionally, we found that HPAI was a sensitive subject among bird owners. Owners of 62 % of eligible case holdings and 55 % of eligible control holdings agreed to participate in the study, with no obvious patterns in the reasons behind declining to participate. The relatively low response rate limited the study population to 18 cases and 34 controls and potentially introduced non-response bias, where non-participants may differ from the study population. The anticipated sample size (24 cases and 48 controls) was not achieved, and this affected the data analysis. We initially selected the source population of cases to potentially include all Danish holdings with primary outbreaks during the considered epidemiological seasons. The source population of controls included all holdings registered in the CHR without outbreaks during the study period. Not all non-commercial holdings are obliged to be registered, and therefore the eligible population for this holding type was limited. However, all commercial holdings must be registered, so we presume that the bias for commercial farms was limited.

Since we collected data in 2023 from three epidemiological seasons (2020/2021, 2021/2022 and 2022/2023), the internal validity of the study may be affected by potential misclassification in the measures of exposure due to recall bias. This is especially true as owners of previous outbreak holdings may remember details around the time of the outbreak better than the owners who did not experience an outbreak. Therefore, owners of previous outbreak holdings may remember observing wild birds around the holding, while the owners not having experienced an outbreak may have failed to notice or recall the presence of wild birds. Misclassification could also be introduced due to response bias if some owners provided answers that they consider better practice than the actual situation (for example due to social desirability bias or liability concerns). We attempted to minimise the risk of these types of biases by assuring the respondents that all data were anonymised and by visually verifying the given response to some questions at the holdings visited.

We matched case and control holdings by size of the holding, type of birds and distance to wetlands and coastal areas, all variables that have been considered as either confounders or risk factors in other studies (size of the holding was identified as a confounder in [Thomas et al., 2005](#); type of production was associated with biosecurity in [Delpont et al., 2021](#); distance to coast and wetlands was associated with HPAI detection in [Kjær et al., 2022](#)). Moreover, with the aim to ensure that cases and controls were temporally aligned, we indirectly matched the time-period by asking the owners or managers of the case holdings about the specific period during which the outbreak was detected, and the owners or managers of the controls about the period during which the outbreak was detected in the matched case. By matching the cases and controls, we aimed to reduce potential confounding with variables used for the matching criteria. However, when applying matching criteria in a case-control study, on one hand, we introduce selection bias and expose the study to the risk of over-matching, which could result in the lack of apparent differences between the case and control groups ([Axelson, 2005](#)). On the other hand, we decided to apply the matching criteria to

ensure that every case had two potential controls that were comparable in terms of production system and management. This was especially relevant since the source population was relatively small and heterogeneous, including both commercial holdings with more than 100 birds and small-scale hobby holdings with less than 100 birds not intended for commercial production.

Unfortunately, the sample size of this study was not deemed sufficient to stratify for additional confounders or investigate biologically meaningful interactions. Therefore, we cannot rule out the possibility of residual confounding, by measured or unmeasured variables. However, if our data were to contain confounding variables, we would expect that those variables were statistically significant in the univariable analysis. Given that the only statistically significant explanatory variable in the univariable analysis was observations of wild waterfowl or gulls, and all other variables were not statistically significant, we did not find indications of confounding. To further assess the potential association between explanatory variables, we visualised the crosstabulations between the statistically significant variable and each of the remaining variables of interest in the study. None of the crosstabulations fulfilled the requirement to have at least five observations in all groups, emphasising the limited data. Additionally, we investigated the risk of procedural confounding in herd size by visually comparing the quantiles of the number of birds in case and control holdings. Some difference in the median number of birds was observed, while there were only small differences in the 75th and 95th percentiles. Therefore, there might be a risk of procedural confounding with herd size, as illustrated by the slight apparent (visual) difference in the distributions of herd sizes in case and control holdings ([Table S2 in Supplementary material 3](#)).

We chose to use the Holm method ([Holm, 1979](#)) instead of the more conservative Bonferroni method to adjust Bayesian p-values in the study for multiple comparisons. This was done to reduce the risk of a statistical Type I error while retaining more statistical power than the Bonferroni method allows. However, since only the smallest crude p-value was statistically significant after correction for multiple comparisons, the outcome of adjusting p-values in this study was the same whether the Holm or Bonferroni approach was used.

4.3. Interpretation and generalisation

Surveillance activities during the study period detected HPAI in more than 700 wild birds, the majority being species of the Anseriformes bird order, followed by Falconiformes and Charadriiformes bird orders. Using data from the Danish national AI surveillance from 2020 to 2021, [Liu et al. \(2024\)](#) found that the bird order Anseriformes and decreasing distance to wetlands were associated with a high risk of AI detection in wild birds. Similarly, [Kjær et al. \(2022\)](#) found that decreasing distance to wetlands and coastal areas was associated with AI detection in wild birds, based on surveillance data from 2006 to 2020. Based on these findings, we matched case and control holdings on distance to wetlands and coastal areas and asked questions specifically about wild waterfowl observations. Since distance to wetlands and coastal areas was one of the matching criteria, we could not test its effect in the current study.

Consistent with our findings, [Green et al. \(2023\)](#) and [Patyk et al. \(2023\)](#) found that sightings of waterfowl or shorebirds in fields surrounding holdings in the United States were associated with an increased risk of HPAI virus infection. [Velkers et al. \(2021\)](#) reported from the Netherlands that densities of certain wild birds were higher in water-rich areas compared to non-water-rich areas, while [Gonzales et al. \(2023\)](#) found an association between the risk of HPAI virus incursion and the presence of specific waterfowl in the vicinity of poultry farms. Similarly, [Schreuder et al. \(2022\)](#) concluded that densities of water-associated bird species were predictors of outbreaks in Dutch poultry holdings, supporting the evidence in our study that the presence of waterfowl or gulls near the poultry or captive bird holding was more common in holdings with a previous outbreak ([Table 9](#)). These findings correspond with the high sequence identity of virus in outbreak holdings

and wild birds, suggesting that wild birds are the source of HPAI virus.

Similar to Thomas et al. (2005), we found no statistically significant differences in the odds of outdoor access and HPAI virus incursion. This could be due to the fact that the Danish veterinary authorities had implemented a national compulsory housing order during 13 of the 18 included outbreaks, where poultry and other captive birds were required to be kept indoors or under a roof, net or wire (Ministry of Food, Agriculture and Fisheries of Denmark, 2020, 2021a, 2021b, 2022a, 2022b, 2023).

We did not find any significant protective effects of the biosecurity measures presented in Table 5. Not using deterrents against wild birds was more common among case holdings compared to control holdings, but the association was not statistically significant at the 5 % level ($p = 0.06$; data not shown). However, other case-control studies found several biosecurity and management measures affected the risk of HPAI infection, including requiring visitors or workers to change clothes before entry (Garber et al., 2016; Green et al., 2023), requiring to shower before entrance and having access to restroom facilities (Patyk et al., 2023), cleaning and disinfecting of entryway into barns (Garber et al., 2016) or of vehicles entering the farm (Green et al., 2023), managing vehicle movements (Garber et al., 2016; Guinat et al., 2020), delimitation of the farm (Green et al., 2023; Guinat et al., 2020) and ceiling/eaves ventilation in the housing (Garber et al., 2016). One potential reason for the discrepancy is the limited sample size in our study, in which some groups had only a small number of observations. The sample size calculation was based on including 24 case holdings, while only 18 case holdings were included in the study. Including 24 case holdings would have allowed us to find significant risk factors with an OR of 4.5, while less potent risk factors would not be expected to be found in a study with such a small sample size. This might explain some of the differences between our study and the references listed above. Furthermore, many biosecurity measures might have limited effect individually, resulting in little effect as protective factors in an analysis, while the combination of biosecurity measures could be a protective factor if all measures are applied at all times. This has been shown in other studies, which indicated that a combination of multiple biosecurity measures must be implemented to reduce the incursion and spread of pathogens (Horvat et al., 2022; Jensen et al., 2021; Zhou et al., 2018), and may explain the lack of statistical significance of the biosecurity measures investigated in this study. Another explanation could be that we matched the size of the holdings and types of birds in the holdings: two variables which could be associated with biosecurity standards.

Outbreaks have been detected in holdings with high biosecurity standards in Denmark and other European countries. However, we were unable to determine the exact route of introduction of HPAI virus in the included case holdings, and a knowledge gap remains. A study from Minnesota showed that there was a lag period of 6–8 weeks between the detection of avian influenza virus in sentinel ducks placed 100–1000 m from turkey holdings and the detection of avian influenza virus in the turkeys (Halvorson et al., 1985). Similar to our study, when exactly the virus was introduced into the holdings was unknown, making it challenging to draw conclusions on the route of introduction. Nonetheless, the presence of HPAI virus in the wild bird population around domestic bird holdings can be considered a proxy for transmission of the virus to domestic birds. Since we could not demonstrate any specific route of introduction, we are unable to provide specific mitigation measures besides considering the placement of poultry and other captive bird holdings. However, especially during periods with increased risk of transmission from wild birds, extra focus on external biosecurity is needed, e.g. rodent control, specific guidance for workers and visitors entering farms, and for visiting trucks. In future case-control studies, the statistical power could be increased by including cases from several countries in the analyses. Additionally, more studies are warranted regarding the effect of land cover and land use around poultry and other captive bird holdings. Based on findings from the Netherlands, Gonzales

et al. (2022) indicated that near proximity of forest around a holding can make the area less attractive to wild waterfowl, and thereby decrease the probability of infectious contact. A better understanding of potentially protective environmental measures would support farmers in making risk-based decisions to reduce the probability of incursion.

5. Conclusions

This case-control study provides evidence of an association between observations of wild waterfowl and gulls in close proximity and the incursion of HPAI virus into poultry and captive bird holdings in Denmark. This finding can be used for future risk management, for example in risk-based monitoring, biosecurity management and placement of captive bird holdings. The results can further be used in quantitative epidemiological models aiming to predict the transmission of HPAI virus from wild birds to captive birds. We also found that HPAI is a sensitive subject among bird owners and therefore any means to increase trust and collaboration between bird owners, veterinary authorities and researchers are recommended.

Funding

The study was co-funded by the Danish Veterinary Consortium (DK-VET) and the European Union's Horizon Europe Project 10113646 EUP AH&W, European Partnership on Animal Health and Welfare.

Institutional review board statement

The Faculty of Health and Medical Sciences approved the processing of personal data up to and including 31 December 2031 (case no.: 514–0825/23–3000), and The Research Ethics Committee for Science and Health approved the study and found it compliant with relevant Danish and International standards and guidelines for research ethics on 22 May 2023 (journal no.: 504–0394/23–5000).

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Helene Ane Jensen: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Matthew Denwood:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis. **Lene Jung Kjær:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Søren Saxmose Nielsen:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Carsten Thure Kirkeby:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Yuan Liang:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis. **Charlotte Kristiane Hjulsager:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis. **Anette Ella Boklund:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank the following people for their valuable contributions to the study: the bird owners and managers who participated in the study; Rasmus Wibrand and Kamilla Mønsted who assisted with data collection; Désirée Jansson at the Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, and Malin Grant, Maria Nöremark and Arianna Comin at the Swedish Veterinary Agency who shared their questionnaire from a similar study conducted in Sweden, which we used as inspiration during the development of our questionnaire; veterinary and scientific officers at the Danish Veterinary and Food Administration who helped

provide information about previous outbreak holdings and gave feedback on our questionnaire; Ida Thøfner, Mie Nielsen Blom and Jens Peter Christensen who gave feedback on our questionnaire; and Sarah Layhe of Vaetta Editing for editing the English language of this paper.

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.prevetmed.2025.106419](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prevetmed.2025.106419).

References

- Axelsson, O., 2005. Negative and non-positive epidemiological studies. *Hum. Ecol. Risk Assess.* 11, 159–167. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10807030590919981>.
- Bregnballe, T., Frederiksen, M., Gregersen, J., 1997. Seasonal distribution and timing of migration of Cormorants *Phalacrocorax carbo sinensis* breeding in Denmark. *Bird. Study* 44, 257–276. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00063659709461062>.
- Busani, L., Valsecchi, M.G., Rossi, E., Toson, M., Ferrè, N., Pozza, M.D., Marangon, S., 2009. Risk factors for highly pathogenic H7N1 avian influenza virus infection in poultry during the 1999–2000 epidemic in Italy. *Vet. J. Lond. Engl.* 197, 171–177. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tvjl.2008.02.013>.
- Central Husbandry Register, 2023. (<https://chr.fvst.dk/chr/faces/frontpage>) (accessed 25 October 2023).
- Danish Veterinary and Food Administration, 2023a. Information regarding avian influenza. <https://en.foedevarestyrelsen.dk/animals/animal-health-/animal-disease/s/avian-influenza>.
- Danish Veterinary and Food Administration, 2023b. Avian influenza preparedness (Fugleinfluenza-beredskab). (<https://ai.fvst.dk/>) (accessed 28 August 2023).
- Delpont, M., Guinat, C., Guérin, J.-L., Le Ieu, E., Vaillancourt, J.-P., Paul, M.C., 2021. Biosecurity measures in French poultry farms are associated with farm type and location. *Prev. Vet. Med.* 195, 105466. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prevetmed.2021.105466>.
- Dick, W.J.A., Piersma, T., Prokosch, P., 1987. Spring migration of the siberian knots *Calidris canutus canutus*: Results of a co-operative wader study group project. *Ornis Scand. Scand. J. Ornithol.* 18, 5–16.
- Elbers, A.R.W., Holtslag, J.B., Bouma, A., Koch, G., 2007. Within-flock mortality during the high-pathogenicity avian influenza (H7N7) epidemic in The Netherlands in 2003: implications for an early detection system. *Avian Dis.* 51, 304–308. <https://doi.org/10.1637/7579-040106R.1>.
- European Food Safety Authority, European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control, European Union Reference Laboratory for Avian Influenza, Adlhoeh, C., Fusaro, A., Gonzales, J.L., Kuiken, T., Marangon, S., Niqueux, É., Staubach, C., Terregino, C., Aznar, I., Muñoz Guajardo, I., Baldinelli, F., 2022. Avian influenza overview December 2021 – March 2022. *EFSA J.* 20. <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2022.7289>.
- European Food Safety Authority, European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control, European Union Reference Laboratory for Avian Influenza, Adlhoeh, C., Fusaro, A., Gonzales, J.L., Kuiken, T., Marangon, S., Niqueux, É., Staubach, C., Terregino, C., Aznar, I., Guajardo, I.M., Baldinelli, F., 2023. Avian influenza overview September – December 2022. *EFSA J.* 21. <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2023.7786>.
- European Food Safety Authority, European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control, European Union Reference Laboratory for Avian Influenza, Fusaro, A., Gonzales, J. L., Kuiken, T., Mirinavičiūtė, G., Niqueux, É., Ståhl, K., Staubach, C., Svartström, O., Terregino, C., Willgert, K., Baldinelli, F., Delacourt, R., Georganas, A., Kohnle, L., 2024. Avian influenza overview December 2023–March 2024. *EFSA J.* 22, e8754. <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2024.8754>.
- European Union, 2016. Regulation (EU) 2016/429 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 9 March 2016 on transmissible animal diseases and amending and repealing certain acts in the area of animal health (Animal Health Law). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/429/oj/eng>.
- Garber, L., Bjork, K., Patyk, K., Rawdon, T., Antognoli, M., Delgado, A., Ahola, S., McCluskey, B., 2016. Factors associated with highly pathogenic avian influenza H5N2 infection on table-egg layer farms in the Midwestern United States, 2015. *Avian Dis.* 60, 460–466. <https://doi.org/10.1637/11351-121715-Reg>.
- Gonzales, J.L., de Freitas Costa, E., Hennen, W.H.G.J., Petie, R., Elbers, A.R.W., 2023. Voorspellend model voor besmettingsrisico van HPAI-virus bij commerciële pluimveebedrijven in Nederland. No. 2301353. Wageningen. *Bioveterinary Res.* <https://doi.org/10.18174/633656>.
- Gonzales, J.L., Hennen, W.H.G.J., Petie, R., de Freitas Costa, E., Beerens, N., Slaterus, R., Kuiken, T., Stahl, J., Elbers, A.R.W., 2022. Risicofactoren voor introductie van HPAI-virus op Nederlandse commerciële pluimveebedrijven, 2014–2022. In: *Wageningen Bioveterinary Research*; No 2211632.
- Green, A.L., Branan, M., Fields, V.L., Patyk, K., Kolar, S.K., Beam, A., Marshall, K., McGuigan, R., Vuolo, M., Freifeld, A., Torchetti, M.K., Lantz, K., Delgado, A.H., 2023. Investigation of risk factors for introduction of highly pathogenic avian influenza H5N1 virus onto table egg farms in the United States, 2022: a case-control study. *Front. Vet. Sci.* 10.
- Guinat, C., Comin, A., Kratzer, G., Durand, B., Delesalle, L., Delpont, M., Guérin, J.-L., Paul, M.C., 2020. Biosecurity risk factors for highly pathogenic avian influenza (H5N8) virus infection in duck farms, France. *Transbound. Emerg. Dis.* 67, 2961–2970. <https://doi.org/10.1111/tbed.13672>.
- Halvorson, D.A., Kelleher, C.J., Senne, D.A., 1985. Epizootiology of avian influenza: effect of season on incidence in sentinel ducks and domestic turkeys in Minnesota. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* 49, 914–919. <https://doi.org/10.1128/aem.49.4.914-919.1985>.
- Holm, S., 1979. A simple sequentially rejective multiple test procedure. *Scand. J. Stat.* 6, 65–70.
- Horvat, A., Luning, P.A., DiGennaro, C., Rommens, E., van Daalen, E., Koene, M., Jalali, M.S., 2022. The impacts of biosecurity measures on *Campylobacter* contamination in broiler houses and slaughterhouses in the Netherlands: A simulation modelling approach. *Food Control* 141, 109151. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2022.109151>.
- Jensen, H.A., Boklund, A.E., Kirkeby, C.T., Kjær, L.J., Hjulsgager, C.K., Larsen, L.E., Nielsen, S.S., 2023. Protocol for a case-control study on risk factors for introduction of highly pathogenic avian influenza into holdings with poultry and other captive birds in Denmark. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10376775>.
- Jensen, M., Jensen, U., Bertelsen, M., 2021. Assessing the effects of biosecurity measures in terrarium management. *J. Zoo. Aquar. Res.* 9, 157–160. <https://doi.org/10.19227/jzar.v9i3.470>.
- Jerry, C., Stallknecht, D.E., Leyson, C., Berghaus, R., Jordan, B., Pantin-Jackwood, M., Franca, M.S., 2021. Age-associated changes in recombinant H5 highly pathogenic and low pathogenic avian influenza hemagglutinin tissue binding in domestic poultry species. *Anim. Open Access J. MDPI* 11, 2223. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani11082223>.
- Kanstrup, N., Asferg, T., Flinterup, M., Thorsen, B.J., Jensen, T.S., 2009. Vildt & landskab. Resultater af 6 års integreret forskning i Danmark 2003–2008 (in Danish). Hornslet Bogtrykkeri, Skov- og Naturstyrelsen.
- Kjær, L.J., Hjulsgager, C.K., Larsen, L.E., Boklund, A.E., Halasa, T., Ward, M.P., Kirkeby, C. T., 2022. Landscape effects and spatial patterns of avian influenza virus in Danish wild birds, 2006–2020. *Transbound. Emerg. Dis.* 69, 706–719. <https://doi.org/10.1111/tbed.14040>.
- Liu, Y., Kjær, L.J., Boklund, A.E., Hjulsgager, C.K., Larsen, L.E., Kirkeby, C.T., 2024. Risk factors for avian influenza in Danish poultry and wild birds during the epidemic from June 2020 to May 2021. *Front. Vet. Sci.* 11. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2024.1358995>.
- Ministry of Food, Agriculture and Fisheries of Denmark (Ministeriet for Fødevarer, Landbrug og Fiskeri), 2020. Ministerial Order on specific preventive measures against avian influenza in poultry and other captive birds (Bekendtgørelse om særlige forebyggende foranstaltninger mod avier influenza for fjerkræ og andre fugle i fangenskab, BEK nr 1707 af 27/11/2020). (<https://www.retsinformation.dk/eli/ta/2020/1707>).
- Ministry of Food, Agriculture and Fisheries of Denmark (Ministeriet for Fødevarer, Landbrug og Fiskeri), 2021a. Ministerial Order on the repeal of the Ministerial Order on prohibition of assembly operations of poultry and other captive birds and the Ministerial Order on specific preventive measures against avian influenza in poultry and other captive birds (Bekendtgørelse om ophævelse af bekendtgørelse om forbud mod samling af fjerkræ og andre fugle i fangenskab og bekendtgørelse om særlige forebyggende foranstaltninger mod avier influenza for fjerkræ og andre fugle i fangenskab, BEK nr 1026 af 27/05/2021). (<https://www.retsinformation.dk/eli/ta/2021/1026>).
- Ministry of Food, Agriculture and Fisheries of Denmark (Ministeriet for Fødevarer, Landbrug og Fiskeri), 2021b. Ministerial Order on biosecurity measures against avian influenza in poultry and other captive birds (Bekendtgørelse om biosikringsforanstaltninger mod avier influenza for fjerkræ og andre fugle i fangenskab, BEK nr 1996 af 01/11/2021). (<https://www.retsinformation.dk/eli/ta/2021/1996>).
- Ministry of Food, Agriculture and Fisheries of Denmark (Ministeriet for Fødevarer, Landbrug og Fiskeri), 2022a. Ministerial Order on the repeal of the Ministerial Order on biosecurity measures against avian influenza in poultry and other captive birds (Bekendtgørelse om ophævelse af bekendtgørelse om biosikringsforanstaltninger mod avier influenza for fjerkræ og andre fugle i fangenskab, BEK nr 541 af 02/05/2022). (<https://www.retsinformation.dk/eli/ta/2022/541>).
- Ministry of Food, Agriculture and Fisheries of Denmark (Ministeriet for Fødevarer, Landbrug og Fiskeri), 2022b. Ministerial Order on biosecurity measures against avian influenza (Bekendtgørelse om biosikringsforanstaltninger mod avier influenza, BEK nr 1445 af 22/11/2022). (<https://www.retsinformation.dk/eli/ta/2022/1445>).
- Ministry of Food, Agriculture and Fisheries of Denmark (Ministeriet for Fødevarer, Landbrug og Fiskeri), 2023. Ministerial Order on the repeal of the Ministerial Order on biosecurity measures against avian influenza (Bekendtgørelse om ophævelse af bekendtgørelse om biosikringsforanstaltninger mod avier influenza, BEK nr 391 af 18/04/2023). (<https://www.retsinformation.dk/eli/ta/2023/391>).
- Ooms, J., 2024. writexl: Export data frames to Excel “xlsx” format. R package version 1.5.0. (<https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=writexl>).
- Otte, J., Nugent, R., 2004. Transboundary animal diseases: Assessment of socio-economic impacts and institutional responses. *Livest. Policy Discuss.* Pap. No 9.
- Patyk, K.A., Fields, V.L., Beam, A.L., Branan, M.A., McGuigan, R.E., Green, A., Torchetti, M.K., Lantz, K., Freifeld, A., Marshall, K., Delgado, A.H., 2023. Investigation of risk factors for introduction of highly pathogenic avian influenza H5N1 infection among commercial turkey operations in the United States, 2022: a case-control study. *Front. Vet. Sci.* 10.
- Plate, K., Knüppel, S., Hornbacher, A., Greiner, M., Müller-Graf, C., 2024. Development of a tool for rapid assessment of the evidence of human observational epidemiological studies with focus on risk of bias in the context of public health and risk assessment. *EFSA Support. Publ* 21, 8925E. <https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2024.EN-8925>.

- Plummer, M., Best, N., Cowles, K., Vines, K., 2006. CODA: Convergence diagnosis and output analysis for MCMC. *R. N.* 6, 7–11. (http://cran.r-project.org/doc/Rnews/Rnews_2006-1.pdf#page=7).
- R Core Team, 2024. R: A language and environment for statistical computing. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria.
- Sargeant, J.M., O'Connor, A.M., Dohoo, I.R., Erb, H.N., Cevallos, M., Egger, M., Ersbøll, A.K., Martin, S.W., Nielsen, L.R., Pearl, D.L., Pfeiffer, D.U., Sanchez, J., Torrence, M.E., Vigre, H., Waldner, C., Ward, M.P., 2016. Methods and processes of developing the Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology - Veterinary (STROBE-Vet) Statement. *J. Vet. Intern. Med.* 30, 1887–1895. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jvim.14574>.
- Schreuder, J., de Knecht, H.J., Velkers, F.C., Elbers, A.R.W., Stahl, J., Slaterus, R., Stegeman, J.A., de Boer, W.F., 2022. Wild bird densities and landscape variables predict spatial patterns in HPAI outbreak risk across The Netherlands. *Pathogens* 11, 549. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens11050549>.
- Shimizu, Y., Hayama, Y., Yamamoto, T., Murai, K., Tsutsui, T., 2018. Matched case-control study of the influence of inland waters surrounding poultry farms on avian influenza outbreaks in Japan. *Sci. Rep.* 8, 3306. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-21695-1>.
- Thomas, M.E., Bouma, A., Ekker, H.M., Fonken, A.J.M., Stegeman, J.A., Nielsen, M., 2005. Risk factors for the introduction of high pathogenicity avian influenza virus into poultry farms during the epidemic in the Netherlands in 2003. *Prev. Vet. Med.* 69, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prevetmed.2004.12.001>.
- Tøttrup, A.P., Pedersen, L., Thorup, K., 2018. Autumn migration and wintering site of a wood warbler *Phylloscopus sibilatrix* breeding in Denmark identified using geolocation. *Anim. Biotelemetry* 6, 15. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40317-018-0159-x>.
- Velkers, F.C., Manders, T.T.M., Vernooij, J.C.M., Stahl, J., Slaterus, R., Stegeman, J.A., 2021. Association of wild bird densities around poultry farms with the risk of highly pathogenic avian influenza virus subtype H5N8 outbreaks in the Netherlands, 2016. *Transbound. Emerg. Dis.* 68, 76–87. <https://doi.org/10.1111/tbed.13595>.
- Walsh, M.G., Mor, S.M., Hossain, S., 2020. Highly pathogenic avian influenza (H5N1) landscape suitability varies by wetland habitats and the degree of interface between wild waterfowl and poultry in India. *Viruses* 12, 1290. <https://doi.org/10.3390/v12111290>.
- Ward, M.P., Maftei, D., Apostu, C., Suru, A., 2008. Environmental and anthropogenic risk factors for highly pathogenic avian influenza subtype H5N1 outbreaks in Romania, 2005–2006. *Vet. Res. Commun.* 32, 627–634. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11259-008-9064-8>.
- Wickham, H., François, R., Henry, L., Müller, K., Vaughan, D., 2023. dplyr: A grammar of data manipulation. R package version 1.1.4. (<https://dplyr.tidyverse.org/>).
- World Organisation for Animal Health, 2021. Chapter 3.3.4. Avian influenza (including infection with high pathogenicity avian influenza viruses). In *Manual of diagnostic tests and vaccines for terrestrial animals*, 8th ed. World Organisation for Animal Health. (<https://www.woah.org/en/what-we-do/standards/codes-and-manuals/terrestrial-manual-online-access/>).
- Zhou, X., Wang, Y., Liu, H., Guo, F., Doi, S.A., Smith, C., Clements, A.C.A., Edwards, J., Huang, B., Soares Magalhães, R.J., 2018. Effectiveness of market-level biosecurity at reducing exposure of poultry and humans to avian influenza: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *J. Infect. Dis.* 218, 1861–1875. <https://doi.org/10.1093/infdis/jiy400>.